

REVIEW OF SOME CASES OF MITIGATION OF PUNISHMENT CHARACTERIZING THE NATURE OF THE CRIME IN THE CRIMINAL LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this thesis, the author analyzes the mitigating circumstances of punishment, which characterize the nature of the committed crime, which is taken into account when prescribing punishment, within the framework of the criminal law of Uzbekistan. The author conditionally divides the punishment mitigation cases into three groups:

a) mitigating circumstances that characterize the nature of the crime: 1) committing a crime as a result of severe personal, family conditions or in another difficult situation; 2) committing a crime due to coercion or dependence on the material side, in terms of service or in other ways; 3) committing a crime in the event of intense mental excitement caused by the; 4) to commit a crime, deviating from the reasonable limit of necessary defense, final necessity, to harm the person who committed a socially dangerous act in the seizure, in reasonable risk associated with professional or economic activity; 5) to commit a crime under the influence of the wrongful or immoral behavior of the victim; b) circumstances that alleviate the punishment that characterize the person who committed the crime: 1) the commission of a minor's Crime; 2) the commission of a crime by a pregnant woman; C) cases of mitigating punishment that characterize the behavior of the offender after the crime is committed: 1) to commit an offense, to express sincere remorse or to actively help to unravel the Crime; 2) to voluntarily eliminate the damage caused.

Keywords: appointment of a sentence, commission of a crime by a pregnant woman, voluntarily eliminate the damage caused, reasonable risk associated with professional or economic activity.

The appointment of a sentence takes into account the circumstances that alleviate the punishment that characterize the nature of the crime committed. In particular, the list of mitigating circumstances is listed in Article 55 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. We can conditionally divide them into three groups:

(a) cases of mitigating punishment that characterize the nature of the crime;

(b) mitigating circumstances of punishment characterizing the person who committed the crime;

(c) cases of mitigating punishment that characterize the behavior of the offender after the commission of the crime.

Let's get acquainted with some of them below.

Committing a crime in the event of a serious personal, family circumstances or other difficult situation (subparagraph "v" of Article 55 (1) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

The fact that committing a crime as a result of severe personal, family circumstances or in another difficult situation is included among the mitigating circumstances was due to the strong influence of certain objective factors on the behavior of the culprit in such situations. M.Rustambayev explained that the law leaves this list open, thereby reflecting various aspects of human activity, and due to this, all other conditions that cannot be listed in the law must be recognized as conditions that alleviate the crime [1].

In this case, ***severe personal conditions*** are understood as conditions associated with a person's illness, profession, service and public activity, as well as such situations as the poor attitude of certain individuals in the person's studies, labor activity and marriage.

Severe family conditions are understood as the illness of one of the family members, the temporary hardship of the family, the bad behavior of one of the family members and other similar situations associated with family members and family life.

Another predicament refers to situations that reduce a person to a difficult situation, which is not related to his severe personal and marital status, including mutual discord with the victim, mental anguish caused by the guilt and bad luck in other matters, as well as other similar situations.

To commit a crime for reasons of coercion or dependence on the material side, in terms of service or in other respects (subparagraph "v" of Article 55 (1) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

In the case of mitigating this punishment, a situation is provided in which the freedom of the culprit to choose his actions is severely limited. According to the content of the law, such a situation occurs as a result of the activities of third parties. In this case, third parties in this way influence the consciousness and will of the culprit, giving impetus to the fact that he committed an illegal act,

which is a sign that the culprit has no radical motives in his actions and no attempt to commit a crime [2].

By mental coercion, it is necessary to understand the use of physical force on the victim, the destruction of his property, the threat of disclosure of information that the victim wants to keep secret, etc. Violence against loved ones of an individual can be applied as a type of mental repression. They can also be stolen, sexually abused, physically repressed [3]. M.Rustambayev notes [4] that mental coercion is intimidation with the use of physical violence against the victim, the loss or damage of their property, and the disclosure of information that the victim wishes to be kept secret, etc.

Physical coercion, on the other hand, is understood to be the transfer of a person's discretion on the part of another person to act or not to do it, that is, physical influence aimed at depriving him of control of his behavior, behavior (associated with forcefully entering a closed room, striking and striking).

Committing a crime in a state of intense mental excitement caused by the victim's acts of violence, severe abuse or otherwise unlawful (subparagraph "d" of Article 55 (1) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

There must be two conditions to apply this punishment mitigating condition:

1) Strong mental embarrassment must have been caused by the victim's acts of violence, heavy abuse or otherwise unlawful;

2) the culprit must be a physiological effect, that is, a state of inability to self-control or disregard conditions under a strong mental shock.

In this case, the guilty mind is not noraso, that is, not crazy, knows the socially dangerous consequence of his act, and therefore is also not exempt from liability, but this case is taken into account when prescribing punishment as a mitigating condition.

Committing a crime, deviating from the reasonable limit of necessary defense, final necessity, causing harm in the seizure of a person who committed a socially dangerous act, at reasonable risk associated with professional or economic activity (subparagraph "e" of Article 55 (1) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

This is reflected in the circumstances that exclude the criminality of the act. One of these is that committing an act in a state of necessary defense, deviating from the limits of necessary defense does not undermine the legal significance of justifying this act, but only causes the recognition of another

crime, which consists in deviating from the scope of necessary defense. The damage to the aggressor can be not only equal to, but also much greater than the damage he intended to inflict. The law speaks only of an imbalance beyond the norm.

Popov pointed out that requiring proportionality to exist between the damage inflicted and the damage received would in practice not have allowed for the necessary defense in a number of cases . A superficial comparison of aggression measures with defensive measures does not give the necessary result, since in this case, the rule applies that the puncher can only be answered with a punch. This rule is not suitable for application in practice. On top of that, there are also types of aggression (e.g. rape), to which the party defending itself cannot respond accordingly [5].

According to the decision of the plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the courts should distinguish the necessary state of defense from the approximate circumstances in which an individual may mistakenly commit such aggression, although there is no clear socially dangerous aggression. If, according to the circumstances of the incident, a person applying defensive measures did not know and could not even know that he was mistaken, his actions should be considered committed in a state of necessary defense [6].

When talking about the capture of a person who committed a socially dangerous act, it should first of all be taken into account that this is a socially useful act aimed at stopping the person in question from committing new crimes and giving him a hold to authorities [7]. Harm to a person who committed a socially dangerous act is justified by the motives and goals of the seizure and its consequences – the elimination of criminal activity, the punishment of the offender, if this is required for his capture.

Here it is important to specify another condition – the specified cases can be found as mitigating circumstances if they are not a component of the disposition of the article of a special part of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, that is, they are not considered signs of a preferential criminal composition [8]. The contents of such crimes include: manslaughter committed beyond the limits of necessary defense or deviating from the limits of necessary measures to apprehend a person who committed a socially dangerous act; intentional infliction of severe or moderately severe health damage committed out of the limits of necessary defense or out of the limits of necessary measures to apprehend a person who committed a socially dangerous act.

Committing a crime under the influence of the wrongful or unethical behavior of the victim (subparagraph “I” of Article 55 (1) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

Currently, crime in most cases acquires a situational character, crimes are committed on the basis of a conflict relationship between the culprit and the victim. Therefore, the study of the identity of the victim, his behavior is one of the tasks of criminal law [9]. A special direction in criminology is engaged in the study of the victim of crime as one of the causes of crime – Victimology. In criminal Genesis, the victim sometimes plays a much larger role. Therefore, it is very important to determine the boundaries of the victim's guilt in the event of a conflict situation that led to the commission of a crime. This allows you to correctly approach the assessment of the guilty person and the level of social danger of the act committed by him and impose a fair punishment on him.

The obscenity of behavior implies the use of violence by the victim, acts involving beatings, humiliation, harsh insults, as well as other acts of the nature of offenses. In this case, the victim can violate both the norms of criminal law and the norms of other areas of law [10].

Illegal or anti-moral actions can be directed not only against the culprit himself, but also against third parties, since the law does not contain any restrictions on this, and the crime committed by the culprit should be directed precisely at the person whose illegal or unethical behavior motivated him. If the crime is directed by the culprit against other persons, the use of this condition as a mitigating condition for punishment, according to the content of the law, should be found unreasonable.

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